

Iran on the Edge: A People's Revolution Beyond Illusions

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The Islamic Republic of Iran is facing one of the most profound crises of its existence. A state that once claimed revolutionary legitimacy has long since lost any meaningful connection to revolutionary ideals. What remains today is not resilience, but the *illusion* of it—maintained through rigid ideology, failed strategies, and escalating violence against its own population.

The protests unfolding across Iran in recent weeks may differ in scale and intensity, but they are not new. They are part of a long historical continuum of resistance—both visible and invisible—that has shaped Iranian society over the past four decades.

A Long History of Resistance

From the very first protests against mandatory hijab laws after the 1979 revolution, to the student movements of the 1990s, the Green Movement of 2009, the Bloody November protests of 2019, and the *Woman, Life, Freedom* movement following the killing of Mahsa (Jina) Amini in 2022—Iranians have repeatedly and consistently raised their voices.

Alongside these large uprisings have been countless smaller acts of resistance: teachers' strikes, labor union statements, letters from political prisoners inside Evin prison, women's everyday defiance, and grassroots campaigns that never made international headlines. Together, these movements and "non-movements" have steadily cracked the walls of what can best be described as a patriarchal, theocratic form of fascism—characterised by an extensive security apparatus, ideological enforcement, and systematic repression of dissent.

It is therefore both inaccurate and dangerous to frame today's protests as the product of foreign intervention or external orchestration by the United States or Israel—a claim too often repeated by the regime and uncritically echoed by some commentators and analysts. Such narratives erase decades of homegrown resistance and, more importantly, actively endanger people on the ground. They provide the Islamic Republic's repression machinery with a ready-made justification to label protesters as "foreign agents" and to imprison, torture, or kill civilians under the pretext of national security.

Each uprising has left deeper fractures in the regime's foundations. Yet the state has refused to learn. Instead of reform, it doubled down—clinging to rigid ideologically driven domestic repression, aggressive foreign policy, the fantasy of sanction-proof resilience, and an obsessive nuclear agenda. Today, those failures have converged into a dark and accelerating crisis.

Why This Moment Is Different

People may initially come to the streets because of economic pressure—as they often do—but in Iran, protests never remain only about bread. They quickly become about decades of denied dignity: freedom, justice, equality, and the right to live without fear.

For anyone who has lived in Iran, it is almost impossible to find someone untouched by state violence. I was stopped and forced into a morality police van before the age of fifteen. My mother was questioned at my school because I asked critical questions in class. As a political science student, I was repeatedly warned about my clothing, silenced in classrooms, shouted down by regime supporters, and ultimately forced to change my thesis topic to remove any reference to women's rights.

This is just one story among millions—and even then, it is the story of someone who still had relative privilege: family support, education, and eventually the ability to continue work outside Iran. Most do not.

We are talking about a country where you can be tortured or killed for what you wear or what you say.

These protests are historic in their scale and inclusivity. Demonstrations are spreading across dozens of cities—including religious centers such as Qom—and bringing together people from diverse generations and backgrounds: students, laborers, parents, grandparents, religious and non-religious alike. Ordinary citizens from every social and economic stratum are standing side by side in the streets, united in their demands for freedom, justice, and dignity. This widespread participation demonstrates that the movement is no longer confined to isolated groups; it reflects a society-wide refusal to accept decades of authoritarian control.

What further distinguishes this moment from previous waves of protest is not only its breadth, but the nature of its demands and the context in which it has emerged. Earlier movements in Iran were often triggered by a singular rupture and consequently articulated around a relatively narrow set of claims: the Green Movement centred on electoral fraud and political rights, while the Woman, Life, Freedom uprising was ignited by the killing of Jina Mahsa Amini and foregrounded women's bodily autonomy and social freedoms. By contrast, the current protests were initially sparked by acute economic shock—most visibly the sudden collapse of the currency—and began in the bazaar, a site historically central to Iran's political economy and to the Islamic Republic's own foundations of power. This economic trigger has facilitated a broader convergence of grievances, drawing in social groups that had previously been insulated from crisis and producing a movement that simultaneously articulates economic, political, and social demands. These dynamics are unfolding amid heightened external pressure, including the shadow of the recent twelve-day war, escalating threats from the United States and Israel, and the weakening of Iran's regional proxies such as Hezbollah and Hamas. Together, these

factors further intensify the regime's crisis of legitimacy and render this protest cycle distinct in both scope and historical context.

State Violence Without Illusion

The images emerging from Iran during every major uprising—2009, *Woman, Life, Freedom*, and now—are real. I saw the violence with my own eyes in 2009. When Neda Agha-Soltan was shot, I was close to the area where I was supposed to meet a friend.

The Islamic Republic of Iran is not simply authoritarian. It is a fascist security machine—with intelligence forces, paramilitary groups, and systematic practices of killing, disappearance, and terror. It hides bodies. It silences families. It commits atrocities that, in scale and brutality, already rival and may exceed what we have seen in Syria.

And it will not fall quietly. If unchecked, it will attempt to drown Iran in blood.

As I write this, Iran has been under a near-total internet blackout for more than 60 hours—an old and deliberate tactic. Since the Green Movement, the regime has understood the power of citizen journalism. It expels foreign reporters, shuts down the internet, and kills in darkness.

Videos now emerging from Iran are devastating. They show rows of dead bodies and scenes of quiet shock rather than chaos—evidence of violence that is systematic, not accidental. Other footage shows hospitals overwhelmed with the wounded, many suffering gunshot injuries to the head and upper body, and corridors filled with families searching desperately for loved ones. Some of these videos have reached the outside world via Starlink connections. It is important, however, to be clear what this does not mean. Starlink is neither widespread nor accessible to most Iranians: it is expensive, rare, and mostly available to large businesses or foreign embassies. Ordinary people—especially in smaller cities and marginalised regions such as Baluchistan and Arab-populated areas—remain cut off and disproportionately targeted.

Despite being cut off from the outside world and pushed into digital darkness, fragments of video emerge from Iran showing groups of brave Iranians gathering at night, chanting slogans of resistance and confronting an oppressive state despite overwhelming force. Some footage captures acts of defiance such as setting fires—symbols of anger and refusal rather than chaos.

Some other videos circulating online show protesters setting fire to mosques, which has led to claims that the movement is anti-Islam. This interpretation ignores context. These acts are not expressions of hostility toward religion, but toward rigidly ideological form of political Islam enforced by the Islamic regime of Iran. For many Iranians inside Iran, mosques have become sites of state surveillance and violence—places where plainclothes security forces, known as Basijis (members of the Basij, a volunteer paramilitary organisation within the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps), are stationed and from which repression is coordinated. This does not justify any forms of destruction and violence, but it helps explain the symbolic meaning such acts carry for people who have paid an enormous price for decades of state-imposed ideology.

An Ethical Question for the World

Many non-Iranian friends ask me: "*What is really going on? Who should we support? It's too complex.*"

To me, this hesitation often reflects not complexity, but ethical avoidance.

You cannot claim to stand for justice, anti-colonialism, or human rights while remaining silent on Iran. For many Iranians, the Islamic regime functions as a colonial power—attacking their identity, culture, freedom, and dignity.

At the same time, Iranians cannot demand global solidarity if they ignore Gaza, Afghanistan, Sudan, Venezuela, or other sites of oppression and violence. Human rights are not selective. Justice is not regional. Solidarity loses meaning when it is conditional.

If we call ourselves human rights, women's rights, or social justice advocates, then we share a common commitment: freedom, dignity, equality, and equity for everyone, regardless of nation, religion, or race. Only through collective solidarity can we confront patriarchal, theocratic, fascist, and colonial systems—wherever they operate.

On Leadership and Confusion

Some outside Iran ask: *Who should we support?* The answer is simple: support the people of Iran.

Yes, you may hear chants referencing Reza Shah or calls for the return of the Pahlavis. This reflects a desire for unity, symbolism, and a counter-force to the current regime—not necessarily a settled consensus on Iran's future system. Even Reza Pahlavi himself has stated he does not seek a future leadership, but wants to support Iranians in overthrowing the Islamic Republic of Iran emphasising preparation for a broad-based transition process ([The Washington Post, Jan 06, 2026](#)).

Historically, a persistent challenge facing Iran's opposition has been the absence of a durable, deliberative coalition capable of articulating diverse political demands into a shared political project oriented toward the dismantling of the Islamic Republic and building a free democratic Iran.

In this context, Reza Pahlavi—son of the former Shah—has emerged as a relatively well-organised political actor in the diaspora. Since the onset of the current protests, he has seized the opportunity and functioned as a coordinating node through which disparate diaspora groups have, to some extent, participated in coordinated mobilisation, often joining calls for gatherings and demonstrations despite ongoing political differences. This participation has coincided with increased visibility, scale, and organisational coherence in transnational mobilisations, and appears to have contributed to renewed momentum and coordination in protests and strikes inside Iran.

At the same time, we also hear other chants that reject all forms of authoritarianism—past and present. The reality is that Iran's society is diverse and heterogeneous. Right now, the future of Iran cannot be decided by anyone—including those of us outside the country. The people on the ground must shape it themselves.

The true leaders of this revolution are not individuals. They are the people in the streets, in prisons, in hospitals, and in graves.

There is no need to pick a single figure or faction, or to let confusion lead to inaction. What matters is to stand with, listen to, and amplify the voices of the Iranian people inside Iran—their pain, their struggle, and their resistance under decades of repression. Iran is a heterogeneous society of over 90 million people, encompassing multiple ethnic, religious, and ideological communities living under a dictatorship that allows little space for open dialogue, free expression, or debate, and where independent media and sustained coverage are systematically suppressed. Many dissenting voices are imprisoned, silenced, or pushed to the margins. Supporting the people of Iran therefore requires understanding the complexity of their reality and responding to their call for dignity, freedom, democracy, and justice—not reducing their movement to a single leader or faction.

Emotion, Unity, and the Risks of Affective Politics

Revolutions are never purely rational. Anger, grief, fear, and hope are powerful political forces—and in Iran today, they are both justified and necessary. Decades of repression have produced an emotional intensity that fuels courage, solidarity, and resistance. This affective energy is not a weakness; it is often what allows people to overcome fear and take to the streets.

But affective politics also carries risks, particularly outside Iran.

In moments of crisis, emotional urgency can create pressure to suspend debate, silence disagreement, and rally unquestioningly around symbols said to represent “unity.” We increasingly hear calls—especially in parts of the diaspora—to postpone political discussion, to “set aside differences for now,” and to avoid criticism in the name of unity. While this may feel stabilising in the short term, it risks replacing collective struggle with symbolic shortcuts.

History shows that revolutions fail not only because of repression, but because critical thinking is deferred too long. When emotional mobilisation overrides discursive politics—open debate, pluralism, accountability—it can narrow a revolutionary movement rather than strengthen it. Suppressing disagreement does not produce unity; it produces conformity. And conformity is the language of authoritarianism, not its antidote.

Our responsibility outside Iran is therefore not to amplify emotion without reflection, nor to police how people express hope or anger. It is to resist the temptation to simplify a complex revolution into a single narrative or solution. Solidarity does not require silence. Unity does not require erasure of difference. A democratic future cannot be built by asking people to stop thinking critically “for now.”

What is needed—inside and outside Iran—is a balance: emotional solidarity with those risking everything on the ground, combined with political responsibility, ethical clarity, and an insistence on pluralism. Anything less risks reproducing the very structures of power this revolution seeks to dismantle.

What Solidarity Actually Means

For those outside Iran who ask what they can do:

1. Remember: this moment is not about *who*—it is about *togetherness* and solidarity.
2. Remember: power does not reside in a single face or name; it resides in the collective courage and consciousness of the people who are in streets of Iran.
3. Our responsibility outside Iran is to:
 - Be the voice of the people inside Iran—their pain, their struggle, and their resistance under decades of repression
 - Be the voice of political prisoners inside Iran
 - Be the voice of activists, unions, and grassroots organisations inside Iran
 - Refuse to reduce a people’s struggle to competing political projects or campaign-driven narratives, which risk sidelining the voices and sacrifices of those resisting on the ground.
4. Demand free and sustained access to the internet for the people of Iran, and support concrete measures to counter state-imposed shutdowns that push millions into digital darkness and enable violence without accountability.
5. Contact your local MPs and representatives and demand concrete political action—not symbolic statements of concern or support.
6. Hold governments accountable when they claim to stand with the people of Iran: follow up, ask what actions have been taken or will be taken, and insist on transparency and responsibility.
7. Pressure governments—such as New Zealand’s—to summon Iranian ambassadors and consider diplomatic consequences.
8. Demand the removal of the Islamic Republic’s representatives from international institutions where they speak against the people they claim to represent.

A People’s Revolution

The current revolution in Iran is a bottom-up movement with an anti-authoritarian focus. It is not leader-centered or individual-centered. It is life- and society-centered; democracy- and freedom-centered, emphasising choice, self-determination, and rights. It is dignity-centered, shaped by decades of pain and resistance. It will move forward only if we stand together.

Woman. Life. Freedom.